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Correlation between the share of taxation in GDP and inequality (Gini coefficient)

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Abstract: Collected revenues from taxes are an important financial resource, for central and local government, in the purpose of carrying out a large area of activities, but at the same time, they have an impact on several socio-economic components. Following the evolution of the changes in the tax data, one can notice their influence on the values of inequality, the correlation between the change in the share of taxes and the increase or decrease of the inequality. The way to measure inequality is the Gini coefficient. In **this paper** the analysis was carried out for the period 2014-2022 and followed the dynamic movement of values, namely the increase or decrease of taxes (% in GDP) and inequality (Gini coefficient), both at the level of European Union and at the level of European Union's Member States. In the analysis of the impact of changes of taxation on inequality (Gini coefficient), data on total taxes and on inequality (Gini coefficient) were used. **The results** obtained show the impact of tax changes (% in GDP) on inequality (Gini coefficient), on each Member Country of the European Union (EU 27) and on each year of the period. **The methodology** used in the paper was: studying the scientific literature in the field, selecting, synthesizing and interpreting the ideas retained through

the own view of the author; collecting data from the European Commission, DG Taxation and Customs Union, based on Eurostat, and Eurostat,. calculations, processing data collected and drawing up the tables necessary for the analyze of the correlation of indicators; analysis of indicators and the correlation between them, for European Union (EU 27), each Member Country of the European Union (EU 27), for each year of the period 2014-2022, and drawing conclusions regarding the final results of the paper.

Keywords: taxation, total taxes share in GDP, Gini coefficient (inequality), correlations, impact, European Union's (EU 27) Member States.

Introduction

Taxes are an important source of budget revenues and one of the key components of fiscal policy. The increase in per capita income, as a result of economic development, gives individuals greater ability to pay taxes and thus, to actively participate in the taxing process. Although revenues from taxes collected from different economic sources are used by the public sector, in various areas, taxes influence the process of economic growth and socio-economic development. (Celikay, 2019).

Tax policy can be considered one of the macroeconomic policies of governments, due to the direct action of fiscal policies, with visible results and economic and social impact. These are elements that motivate governments to move more strongly towards issues concerning taxation (Parthasarathi, 1995).

Collected revenues are an important financial resource, for central and local government, in financing and carrying out a large area of activities, but at the same time, they have an impact on several socio-economic components. (Celikay, 2019, Macek, R. 2018)

The paper followed aspects related to the analysis of the correlation between the change in taxation (% in GDP) and the Gini coefficient (inequality), to observe the influence of taxation changes, on inequality (Gini coefficient) respectively, the correlation between the change in the share of taxes in GDP and the increase or decrease of the Gini coefficient (inequality). The study of the data was carried out both for Eurpean Union and for the Member States of the European Union (EU 27), during the years 2014-2022.

Research Results

The analysis of the impact of changes in total taxes on the level of inequality (Gini coefficient)

The topic of taxes and income inequality has been pursued in various theoretical studies, some of which being mentioned below.

The OECD considers that income inequality results from different ways in which income is distributed among the population. (OECD, Income inequality, <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/indicators/income-inequality.html>). The way to measure inequality is the Gini coefficient. It compares the cumulative proportions of the population with the cumulative

proportions of revenue it receives. It varies between 0, in the case of perfect equality (that is, each share of the population receives the same share of income) and 1, in the case of perfect inequality (that is, all incomes go to the individual with the highest revenue) (OECD) (OECD, Income Inequality, <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/indicators/income-inequality.html>).

Various studies note the relation between inequality and economic growth. In this regard, Lewis (1954), Kuznets (1955) and Kaldor (1956) (quoted by Muinelo-Gallo and Roca-Sagales, Richard L. Bertrand Edt., 2011) The growth models of Lewis (1954), Kaldor (1957), and Pasinetti (1962), Galor, and Moav (2004), which show the favorable impact of inequality, on economic growth are identified, (quoted by Muinelo-Gallo, Roca-Sagales Oriol, Bertrand Edit., 2011)

Other studies note the relation between fiscal policy and income redistribution, which is seen as a tool in ensuring income redistribution. (Clements et. al. 2015, p. 3) (Brinca et al. 2021 ; Caminada et al. 2019 ; Cevik și Correa-Caro 2020 ; Dotti 2020 ; Salotti și Trecroci 2018) (citat de Manwar Hossein and Pathranarakul, Fendel Edt., 2022). (quoted by Manwar Hossein and Pathranarakul, 2022).

Following, in the evolution, the changes in the taxation data, one can notice their influence on the values of inequality, the correlation between the change in the share of taxes and the increase or decrease of the Gini coefficient (inequality). The analysis was carried out for the period 2014-2022 and followed the dynamic movement of values, namely the increase or decrease of taxes (% in GDP) and inequality (Gini coefficient).

The period considered in the analysis took into account the years in which the statistical data provided information for both indicators (taxes, Gini coefficient). For the analysis of the indicators, data were used: data from the European Commission, DG Taxation and Customs Union, based on EUROSTAT data, https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/taxation/economic-analysis/data-taxation-trends_en; Gini coefficient of equivalised available income by age, EUROSTAT https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_di12/default/table?lang=en.

There was a different correlation between the percentage changes in taxes from one year to another (increase or decrease) and the income inequality ones (Gini coefficient), which reflects the impact of the change in taxes, on the level of inequality (Gini coefficient):

1. Increase in taxation (taxes % of GDP) and decrease in inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed:
 - a) in positive values (taxes) and negative values (Gini coefficient), respectively, by increasing total taxes and reducing inequality (Gini coefficient);
 - b) only in positive values, through a higher tax increase and a less inequality increase (Gini coefficient).
 - c) a less taxation increase (total taxes) and a higher inequality increase (Gini coefficient), expressed in positive values.
2. Reduction of taxation (taxes % of GDP) and increase in inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed:

- a) by negative values (total taxes) and positive values (Gini coefficient) respectively;
- b) only by negative values, by a greater reduction in the share of taxes and a smaller decrease in inequality (Gini coefficient).
- c) a lower reduction of the share of taxation (taxes) and a greater reduction of inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed in negative values.

At European Union level (EU - 27)

There has been a continuous increase in total taxes, except for the years 2015, 2019, 2022, when the evolution was negative. The highest increase was recorded in 2021, of 0.39 pp. and the lowest in the year 2020 of 0.06 p.p.; the maximum decrease is observed in 2022 by 0.23 p.p.

At the Gini coefficient there is a continuous decrease, in the period, except for 2018, 2021, when the evolution was increasing. Compared to previous years, the maximum level of decrease was observed in 2022, of -0,6 pp and, respectively, the lowest, of -0,1 p.p., in 2015.

Following the evolution of the two phenomena, one can notice a reverse movement of them, respectively, an increase in taxation corresponded to a decrease in inequality - the Gini coefficient (example years 2016, 2017, 2020), a greater decrease in taxes and lower or equal decrease in inequalities (years 2015, respectively 2020) or the reverse situation (a lower tax decrease and a greater or equal decrease of inequalities) - the year 2021; in the year 2022, with the largest decrease in taxation - 0.23 p.p., the inequality occurs with the greatest decrease of - 0.60 p.p.

At the level of EU Member States (27)

Throughout the period analysed, in all 27 Member States of the European Union, there were both increases and decreases, from one year to the another, of total taxes, as follows [Table 1]:

Table 1

Increases and decreases in total taxes by European Union countries

Countries	Years of increase	Total years	Years of decrease	Total years
Bulgaria	2015, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022	7	2018	1
Greece	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2020, 2021, 2022	7	2019	1
Poland	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	7	2022	1
Slovakia	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	7	2022	1
Germany	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021	6	2020, 2022	2
Estonia	2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	6	2017, 2022	2
Lithuania	2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	6	2017, 2022	2
Luxembourg	2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022	6	2015, 2020	2
Portugal	2015, 2017, 2018, 2020, 2021, 2022	6	2016, 2019	2
Romania	2015, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022	6	2016, 2017	2
Czech Republic	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2020	5	2019, 2021, 2022	3
Spain	2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	5	2015, 2016, 2022	3

Croatia	2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2022	5	2017, 2020, 2021	3
Netherlands	2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020	5	2015, 2021, 2022	3
Austria	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021	5	2016, 2020, 2022	3
Slovenia	2015, 2016, 2018, 2020, 2021	5	2017, 2019, 2022	3
Cyprus	2017, 2018, 2019, 2021	4	2015, 2016, 2020, 2022	4
Latvia	2015, 2016, 2017, 2020	4	2018, 2019, 2021, 2022	4
Sweden	2015, 2016, 2017, 2021	4	2018, 2019, 2020, 2022	4
Belgium	2017, 2018, 2022	3	2015, 2016, 2019, 2020, 2021	5
Denmark	2019, 2020, 2021	3	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2022	5
Ireland	2016, 2021, 2022	3	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020	5
France	2017, 2020, 2022	3	2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2021	5
Italy	2019, 2020, 2022	3	2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2021	5
Hungary	2015, 2016, 2022	3	2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	5
Malta	2016, 2018, 2021	3	2015, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2022	5
Finland	2015, 2016, 2021	3	2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2022	5

Processing based on data from European Commission, DG Taxation and Customs Union, based on Eurostat data https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/taxation/economic-analysis/data-taxation-trends_en; Eurostat Gini coefficient of equivalised disposable income by age, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_di12/default/table?lang=en.

As shown in the table above, in the analyzed period, there were increases in dynamics, in tax and, respectively, reductions, over different periods, grouped by countries:

- 4 countries had tax increases, over a period of seven years, each of them and reductions of them, over a period of one year;
- 6 countries have tax increases over a period of six years, each of them and correspondingly, decreases over a period of two years;
- 6 countries had tax increases, for a period of five years, each of them and reductions for a period of three years;
- 3 countries have tax increases over a period of four years, each of them and decreases of it, over a period of four years;

- 8 countries have tax increases over a period of three years and, respectively, tax decreases, over a five years period.

By countries, the effects of the change in taxation (total taxes % of GDP) and the impact on inequality (Gini coefficient) in the six situations are as follows:

- Position 1a) Increase in taxation (taxes % of GDP) and decrease in inequality (Gini coefficient).

With the exception of Malta, all Member States of the European Union have tax increases on intervals between 1 and 6 years, which have influenced in the direction of inequality reduction. The country with the highest number of tax increase situations associated with Gini coefficient decrease is Poland - six years, followed by Lithuania and Slovenia - five years, the rest of the countries having small-interval changes, respectively 1.2 years.

- Position 1b) Higher tax increase (% in GDP) and lower inequality increase (Gini coefficient).

It includes 15 countries, for three of them (Cyprus, France, Netherlands) the phenomenon of higher tax increases and lower increase in inequality (Gini coefficient) manifesting over the period of two years, the rest of the countries having this situation, each, only for one year of the interval.

- Position 1c) Lower tax increase (% in GDP) and a higher inequality increase (Gini coefficient).

It comprises 19 countries where the lower tax increase is correlated with a higher Gini coefficient increase. Most situations occur in Bulgaria, on the interval of five years, at the rest of 16, the phenomenon occurs in the period of 1-2 years.

- Position 2a) Reduction of taxation (taxes % of GDP) and increase in inequality (Gini coefficient).

Of the total European Union countries - EU 27, a number of 18 countries show a reduction in total taxes and an increase in the Gini coefficient. The highest number of manifestations is identified at: France, Italy and Finland that present such changes on the interval of four years, each; at the rest of the countries the situations occur for periods of 1-3 years, each.

- Position 2b): Higher tax reduction (% in GDP) and lower inequality reduction (Gini coefficient).

It includes a number of 12 countries where the tax decrease is higher than the inequality decrease (Gini coefficient); in one country - Malta, the situation occurs for 3 years, and in the others, for a period of 1-2 years, each.

- Position 2c): Lower reduction of the share of taxation (taxes % of GDP) and a greater reduction of inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed in negative values.

A number of 16 countries have tax reductions, the impact of which resulting in a higher reduction in inequality (Gini coefficient). As a rule, in four countries the changes are registered for a number of years, each (Ireland, Italy, Romania, Sweden), and in the rest of the countries these aspects occur only in one year, for each.

Conclusions

The analysis followed the correlation between the change in taxes (% in GDP) and the values of the Gini coefficient (inequality), respectively, their increase or decrease for the Member States of the European Union (EU 27). The study of the data was carried out during the years 2014-2022.

In the analysis of the impact of changes of taxation and on inequality (Gini coefficient), data on total taxes (% in GDP) and on inequality (Gini coefficient) were taken into account.

The impact of changes in total taxes on the level of inequality.

The analysis of the data was carried out on each Member Country of the European Union and on each year of the period. It resulted that the change in taxation in the form of total taxes influenced the level of the Gini coefficient, according to the following:

1. Increase in taxation (taxes % of GDP) and decrease in inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed:
 - a) in positive values (taxes) and, respectively, negative values (Gini coefficient) ;
 - b) only in positive values, through a higher tax increase and a lower inequality increase (Gini coefficient).
 - c). a lower taxation increase (taxes) and a higher inequality increase (Gini coefficient), expressed in positive values.
2. Reduction of taxation (taxes % of GDP) and increase of inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed:
 - a) by negative values (taxes) and positive values (Gini coefficient), respectively;
 - b) only by negative values, by a higher reduction in the share of taxes and a lower decrease in inequality (Gini coefficient).
 - c). Lower reduction of the share of taxation (taxes) and higher reduction of inequality (Gini coefficient), expressed in negative values.

Grouping the countries by type of manifestation of the impact of the change in taxation on inequality, shows the following:

The most common situation is that of raising total taxes, with the effect of reducing inequality, aspect that is found in 26 EU countries (except Malta), on different time intervals.

The other situations of tax increase (higher or lower), with an impact of increase of inequality (Gini coefficient) (lower and higher, respectively) are found in a smaller number of countries - 15 and, respectively, 19 countries.

The reduction of total taxes with an impact of increasing in inequality (Gini coefficient) is found in 18 countries.

The other situations, the reduction of taxes (higher or lower) with diminishing impact (lower and respectively, higher,) of inequality (Gini coefficient) occurred in 12 countries and 16 countries, respectively.

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